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DISC2024

**Faculty of Technical Sciences
University of Novi Sad**

Hybrid event

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Novi Sad, Serbia

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Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

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LOAEL FOR SIX SERIES OF NEW SUCCINIMIDE DERIVATIVES: IN SILICO SURVEY

Pinter D.¹, Milanović M.¹, Vrkić A.¹, Vidović D.¹, Jovičić-Bata J.¹, Banjac N.², Milošević N.¹

¹Univeristy of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharamcy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21 000 Novi Sad, Serbia
(e-mail: 904009d23@mf.uns.ac.rs)

¹Univeristy of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Food Technology and Biochemistry, Nemanjina 6, Zemun, 11080
Belgrade, Serbia

Abstract:

Succinimide moiety is known for various pharmacological effects including antiepileptic, antiproliferative, analgesic, antipsychotic, anticholinesterase, antioxidative, antifungal etc. Continual research and structural modification of existing succinimide derivatives led to design of six new series (A-F) of succinimides with various polarity, lipophilicity and aqueous solubility. Some of the derivatives have already proven with antiproliferative and antimicrobial activity. Given their possible application, their lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) become one of the most important parameter for further preclinical studies. A total of 71 succinimide derivatives was tested through the free online tool pkCSM for LOAEL (Oral Rat Chronic Toxicity) expressed in log of mg/kg per body weight/day. The lipophilicity expressed as logP and aqueous solubility given as logS were determined through the preADMET online software. All observed compounds had LOAEL between 1.041 and 2.500 log mg/kg per body weight/day with the highest LOAEL for the least lipophilic series C (1.496-2.500) and D (1.442-2.499) and the lowest LOAEL for the most lipophilic series B (1.041-1.868) and F (1.110-1.847). The obtained results indicated statistically significant variations of the LOAEL values between the series depending on their substituents. The LOAEL was statistically significant reversely associated with lipophilicity given as logP of the analysed compounds ($r^2=0.303$, $p<0.001$), as the more lipophilic the succinimide derivative is, the lower LOAEL was determined. On contrary, there was positive association between LOAEL and solubility given as logS of the compounds observed ($r^2=0.310$, $p<0.001$) with compounds of higher aqueous solubility expressing higher LOAEL. The LOAEL of succinimide derivatives is strongly governed by their lipophilicity and aqueous solubility and depends on the substituents attached to their core. More lipophilic compounds and those with more polar substituents and thus more soluble in polar (aqueous) environment are expected to exhibit lower LOAEL.

Keywords: LOAEL; succinimides; lipophilicity; aqueous solubility